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DESIGN INTO LIFE
WHY APPLY DESIGN TO THE ELEMENTARY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper tries to illustrate the relevance of design for public education and evaluates its prospects and applicability in the context of German elementary education. German education is subject to intensive debates. The model it is based on (industrialism and academicism) does no longer answer the needs of current and future societies. Design, as an approach, has the potential to re-imagine education to better suit those needs and to link it to questions and challenges of daily life.

The research for this paper was developed by reviewing literature, observations in elementary schools, interviews with teachers and collecting international cases of design application in public education.

This work reports some of the observed problems and chances in elementary education in Germany, lists intrinsic design characteristics and the possible impacts they could have on general education and, upon reflection of these findings, proposes a method of how and a rationale for why design could be used as a pedagogic strategy.

Keywords: Design; Education; Children

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the design history the intrinsic value design could offer to educate people in its entirety, was of big interest and subject matter of controversial discussions. Today, designers work in as diverse fields redesigning education like architecture, products, technology, services, and pedagogy and with the involvement of all stakeholders create strategies for the future. The master research projects “A culture of learning in urban context” and “How do we learn design”

developed at Köln International School of Design tackle the interface of design and education from different perspectives. This paper presents the findings of a common first research phase on design, design thinking and design education and its contextualization in German elementary education.

The research is based upon three hypotheses that defend the application of design to the context of education: Design is related to “Alltagskultur” and joins theory and daily issues; it enables an overall understanding of real life issues regarding economical, political and social contexts, and, it is solution-oriented and structures knowledge to be applied on a certain project.

CONTEXTUALIZATION

SOCIAL CONTEXT

Today’s society can be characterized by the rapid changes it is facing. Among other sociologists, Saskia Sassen and Richard Sennett has been researching these changes and shifts from two different perspectives. Saskia Sassen (2001) has been observing and researching the dynamics of the global society and global cities since 1980 and did register an increasing acceleration of movements in society. Richard Sennett (2007) has been observing the institutional and organisational change that took place over the last years and the effect it had on each person. He found that today’s ideal model of the global acting, short-termed, complex organization, driven by technological innovations, demands high-flexible workers that easily respond to new requirements and break with habits and the past. Sennett brings in the example of an average employee who, these days, has to learn new skills about every 8 to 12 years, whereas 40 years ago, an

employee might have started at one company right after school and followed the same routine until retirement. These changes of positions and residences result in a fragmentation of former social structures and social instability. Because of these problematics, Sennett (2007) describes today's ideal person as an individual that constantly refreshes its knowledge base, gains new skills and has the ability to handle short term relationships instead of stable social relations.

Besides its rapid changes, today's society can be characterized by its interconnectedness. Angeli Sachs (2010) describes the complex global structures as an interplay of political, economical, technological, ecological and cultural processes. The globalized world already had to face great economical, ecological and social challenges, like the financial crisis (SACHS, 2010) and will have to face in the future. These challenges are unforeseen and cannot be addressed with predefined solutions, rather they demand new collaborations and ways of thinking.

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

The complexity of society is reflected in its data and information overflow. As previously described by different authors (ROBINSON, 2001; FONTOURA, 2002; BONILLA, 2005) developments in technology and information media have led to information overload and media overflow. While Children tend to adopt more readily to new technologies they are at the same time not immune to information overload when using various media, such as TV, Internet, Games etc. The overwhelming accessibility of information can lead to a dearth of understanding due to an inability to filter, select, analyze and criticize the input.

In contrast to this highly visual media environment, a teacher set in a formal school environment struggles to catch the students attention. The school seems alienated to the childrens surrounding environment. (ROBINSON, 2001) Determining the factors that vie for student attention and how to overcome such distractions within the classroom is an important debate within educational theory.

“ALLTAGSKULTUR”

Not only the global context, the changes and challenges in society as mentioned above, has high impact on children, their lives and the way they should be educated. Also their local environment, social structures and day-to-day experiences. In this paper we refer to this social, economical and environmental context as “Alltagskultur”: The totality of characteristic things, conditions and rituals of the everyday life, created by a society. (Duden, 2011)

“Alltagskultur” changes over time. It is a living and complex system compounded by diverse codes which has to be decoded and learned by each person in order to well interact with and survive in it. Saviani (1991) explains that the result of this interaction can be material “tangible” or non-material “intangible”. The material outcome is products (the artificial world), the non-material outcome is culture (rituals, music, arts, etc) and knowledge (scientific, empiric, etc). The environment is reinvented: the reality changes and new ways of interaction are established (new codes); with this new reality, making the whole learning process happen over and over again.

School education has to respond on the “Alltagskultur” of the children. The proposed shift lies in the idea of embedding the “Alltagskultur” and by doing so to give meaning to the well structured academic knowledge.

HYPOTHESES

This work is a review of a strategy to counteract the growing alienation of education with the “daily-real-life” and to educate children for the global social, economic and ecologic challenges they are going to face. It is a strategy that has already been applied in different contexts and ways: The use and application of Design in schools.

Design today is not only used as a creative way of shaping objects, communication or processes but is understood to be problem-solving in various contexts and disciplines, like business, engineering or even health innovation (BROWN, 2009). The design process is also being applied to the context of education. Our

research is based on three hypotheses that state the relevance and need for design in education:

- Design is related to “Alltagskultur” and bridges the gap between education and the outer world. By this, it can be a way to perceive the world and an approach to life.
- Design is interdisciplinary - it enables an overall understanding of local and global economical, political and social contexts.
- Design is solution-oriented and structures knowledge to be applied on a certain project. By restructuring, it can innovate.

GERMAN EDUCATION

HISTORY

To understand German education in the beginning of the 21st century, one need to understand how the school system developed through the last centuries.

Until the 19th century German education was in the hand of confessional institutions and the church formed the perception of reality. The development and building of public schools arose as part of the modernization and restructuring of society. (TENORTH, 2003) Industrialization was driving the change and led to the need of a public education system, that would produce a new workforce.

The intellectual model of academicism, became the counterpart to the economic model of Industrialism. According to Robinson (2001) the German education system, as all western education systems, is based upon these two interrelating models, based in the Enlightenment period.

The production of knowledge and the production of workforce as key concept of public schools was implemented through a rigid school structure. Talking about Germany under Bismarck in the end of 19th century, military structures were being applied to schools, companies, institutions and main areas of society. Companies started to function like armies, with every employee fulfilling a special role. Schools were standardized - the way they operated and the content of what they were teaching. (SENNETT, 2007)

This system was put into question in the beginning of the 20th century by theorists of progressive education. They criticised, that the subject of education was not the child and that education reduced the children´s world to artificial methods, charts and reading (TENORTH, 2003).

Although the German school system was undergoing great discussions and reforms in the 60s and 70s, Helmut Fend in 1980 (in Tenorth, 2003) still defined the qualification for a job and socialization, as a way of teaching expected behavior, two of the four classic school functions.

Today German schools have the educational mandate to teach basic cultural knowledge and prepare the students for future education/studies (KLEMM, VAN ACKEREN, 2011). New guidelines, released by the German Ministry of Education in 2008, no longer put the teaching of specific knowledge at the core of education, but the teaching of competencies. These new guidelines can be understood as a response to the above mentioned rapid changes in society. Explicit aim of this approach is to educate students to become autonomously learning individuals, capable to adapt to changing environments.

THE SCHOOL SYSTEM

The German school system is characterized by the transition from elementary to secondary school. Four to six years (depending on the state) all children visit elementary education, before then being split up into different secondary school types.

Recommendations on which school type to visit are made by the teachers upon an evaluation of the pupils cognitive learning skills. Though studies prove, that this is not the fact. (KLEMM, VAN ACKEREN, 2011)

Depending on the state, the German school system offers the following secondary school types:

The *Hauptschule* (Secondary Modern) provides basic general education and offers the possibility to graduate with the lowest of all possible qualifications. It has the image to be a place for “left-overs”, what discourages German parents to send their children there. (FUHR, 1997).

The *Realschule* (Intermediate school) offers a bigger and broader content, however it is more narrowed to practical activities. After their graduation, pupils are supposed to take on middle-level jobs. Concerning social aspects, the *Realschule* mixes different social classes. (FUHR, 1997).

The *Gymnasium* (Grammar school) offers the highest school education. It covers a broader quantity of content (for instance, more foreign languages) as well as deeper knowledge acquisition. It is supposed to prepare pupils both for university or non-scholarly professions. Pupils graduate with an Abitur, the qualification to ingress in German Universities. (FUHR, 1997).

The *Gesamtschule* (Comprehensive school) combines all three school types and offers the possibility to graduate with any of the above listed qualifications. (KLEMM, VAN ACKEREN, 2011)

ELEMENTARY EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND CHANCES

As already shortly outlined above, German elementary education is of special importance in the school system, because it is the only school type that all children visit, unregarded their learning type, social status or nationality. All elementary teachers we interviewed regarded this as the biggest chance as well as the biggest challenge they face.

The selection process puts high responsibility on elementary teachers. Although a correction of their recommendation is supposed to be possible throughout the school career, studies prove, that their judgement or misjudgement is unlikely to be compensated. The school system is claimed to be permeable for students to move upwards the system. But facts tell, that children rather move the other way. A study conducted in 2006/2007 showed, that out of 50.000 children changing school type (*Hauptschule, Realschule, Gymnasium*), only 20% changed to a higher education form whereas about 80% move to a less challenging school type. (KLEMM, VAN ACKEREN, 2011)

This shows that the selection process in the end of the *Grundschule* can lead to irreversible waste of talents. (ROBINSON, 2009) Moreover, as comparative

studies revealed, it can result in lower self-confidence of the children. (KLEMM, VAN ACKEREN, 2011) This waste of talents becomes even more obvious, with regard to new findings that state the overlapping of competencies between the different school types.

Lately the system is undergoing phases of critique and change and a tendency towards a two-part system can be foreseen. (KLEMM, VAN ACKEREN, 2011) But still elementary school will remain unique in its function to educate all children. The challenges going ahead with this task - the teaching of slow learners together with fast learners and non-native-speakers with children with special needs - turned German elementary schools into the most progressive schools in Germany.

To briefly summarize the above, there is three main reasons to implement design in German elementary schools:

Elementary school is the only type of school that all children do visit, no matter social status, learning skills etc. This is also the reason why school lessons have to be particularly catching and adoptable to all different skills and needs, so that no child is being left behind. And last, the current changes in elementary education in Germany might open it for the idea of design, so that the implementation seems more than realistic.

DESIGN AS AN APPROACH

WICKED PROBLEMS

The academic mind set gives the opportunity mostly to deal with one kind of problem, the tame problem. Conklin (2001 cited in Ritchey, 2005) lists its characteristics: tame problems are problems that are well defined; have clear and assessable solutions (right and wrong); share similarities with other problems; and have solutions that can be tried and discarded. In school class, pupils mainly have to deal with these tame problems, being assessed themselves based on the quantity of right answers.

Robinson (2001) points out that although dealing with tame problems (based on an analytic-deductive process) is necessary and has lead humanity to great advances, these problems are not the unique kind of

problems people face in daily life. Problems of daily life, in this paper referred to as “Alltagskultur”, cannot be answered by one single solution, indeed they are complex and can be approached through different ways. These complex or ill-defined problems are called “wicked problems” by Rittel and Webber (1973 cited by Ritchey, 2005 and Cross, 2006).

A wicked problem cannot be analyzed or broken down to define one perfectly structured solution. No problem-solving strategy can be applied, nor a solution-oriented one. Cross (2006) explains that in order to deal with those ill-defined problems it is rather necessary “to learn to have self-confidence to define, redefine and change problem-as-given in the light of the solution that emerges from their minds and hands” (pg. 07). Thus, tackling the problem is more an issue of constant experimentation than of deep analysis. In contrast to tame problems, no predefined knowledge can be learned, memorized and reproduced in order to solve a wicked problem, instead gained knowledge and past experiences provides inspiration to deal with them. Moreover empiric findings and scientific knowledge serve as a kind of inspirational material on the process of problem solving instead of as recipe.

Robinson (2001) predicts that succeeding generations will have to face even more complex problems: for instance will environmental issues be even more present in their lives once natural resources will be more scarce. Thus he suggests to accredit the next generation with the ability to deal with wicked problems and to engage and stimulate childrens talents.

DESIGN THINKING

Plenty of models and frameworks have been presented as approaches to solve wicked problems, to provide “out-of-the-box” solutions, to innovate or simply to stimulate creativity. Both, academics and companies provide lists of success cases where specific methods have supposedly generated impressive results in terms of new products or technologies. The so called “Design Thinking” stands as one of them.

Brown (2009) and Cross (2006) both point out that this way of thinking (or knowing) cannot exclusively be used by educated designers. Moreover they explain that most people does have a natural aptitude to develop the intrinsic competencies/ characteristics of a design thinker. Various characteristics have been defined by Tim Brown (2009) to be intrinsic to design thinking, from which we want to highlight four as the key concepts: integrative thinking, openness to experiment, collaborative work and modeling.

A designers problem-solving process is not linear neither exclusive. The whole process is a combination of divergent and convergent thinking, of phases of experimentation and analysis. (BROWN, 2009) Cross (2006) remarks that this need to be open and to experiment arises from the nature of wicked problems: once they are ill-defined, “some of the relevant information can only be found by generating and testing solutions”(pg 19). Brown even claims that design thinking is exploratory and largely relies on tacit knowledge and personal experiences. Proposals to the problem do not aim to solve it, but instead configure questions that have not been posed before in order to better understand the problem dimensions and aspects. Finally the integrative thinking does go ahead with the possibility of failure. The openness throughout the process leads to new findings and possible new solutions but also to failures. This open space for experiments does play an important role for the well development of ideas and solutions.

Moreover high complexity or wicked problems demand approaches from different perspectives, as they can´t be assigned to certain spheres of competence. There is a need for multi-disciplinary (interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary) work that combines general as well as special knowledge on the problem. Therefore collaboration takes place as an intrinsic element of the design way of thinking.

Distinctive to the field of design is also its “language”: while the language of the sciences is numeracy and of the humanities is literacy, the main language used by the designers is “modeling”. Cross (2006) and Fontoura (2002) present it as the process

of encoding and communicating ideas and abstract concepts through a tangible or intangible product (2D or 3D), the technical skills related to communicate through objects are individual. The media changes due to the need of the project and the preference of the designer.

In summary, design thinking can be understood as a tool: to learn and understand reality; to connect and use scientific and empirical knowledge/information/data through a tacit framework; in order to produce and to experiment solutions communicated by prototypes and visualizations.

DESIGN IN SCHOOLS

To understand the meaning that design can have in school education, it seems important to refer once again to the different connotations design can have. As mentioned above, this paper focuses on design thinking, a thinking model derived from a designers way of thinking and acting and dealing with wicked problems.

In the report on 'Design in General Education' by the Royal College of Art published in 1979 Bruce Archer and his colleagues call it 'the collected experience of the material culture, and the collected body of experience, skill and understanding embodied in the arts of planning, inventing, making and doing'. (cited in Cross, 2006)

This does not exclude the idea of implementing design as a subject (design history, product design etc) to the school curriculum, but is not the focus and idea of this work. Rather the intrinsic value of design for elementary education is of interest for this paper. Crafting skills, that are usually related to design education, are in this context less relevant for the overall understanding.

DESIGN AS A THIRD AREA OF EDUCATION

Sciences and humanities are usually the two main areas that are taught at schools. They represent two ways of thinking and two perspectives on the world. The focus though lies on the teaching of sciences with its objective and rational perspective on the natural world and its steady search for truth. The solution finding process in the sciences is linear with

only one possible solution to aim for, which does not leave any flexibility or possibility to fail. In the humanities the human experience is core of a subjective and committed research. (CROSS, 2006).

Cross (2006) introduces Design as a third area in education. He proposes that it can complement the sciences and humanities. Its focus is the artificial world and the approach to it is practical. Design does offer strategies to not only create but also to deal with the artificial world and the children's "Alltagskultur" and wicked problems. Embedded in the school curriculum, design thinking can enable students to not only apply knowledge and methods but to respond to problems individually. Harahan already in 1978 claimed that design education must be a reflection on the continuous change and growth of real life. (HARAHAN, 1978). That clearly differentiates the design process from the unreal rigid and linear structure of the sciences.

As already stated above designers have a different use of language to express knowledge, than the sciences and the humanities do. Whereas the sciences and humanities are limiting thoughts to numeracy and literacy, design is visual and by this captures intuitive thoughts as well as it is a tool to visualize information and knowledge. (CROSS, 2006)

This second characteristic became of even bigger importance in times of media and information overflow. The selection, decoding, structuring and visualizing of information became of great importance, especially in problem solving processes. J.T. Mitchell calls this change from literary knowledge transfer to visual knowledge transfer the „Picture Theory" and states that a society's discourse through knowledge is closely linked to the visualization/preparation of knowledge itself (in Meier, 2003).

HOW TO EMBED DESIGN IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION?

Three ways to embed design in elementary education can be identified:

- Design as a subject can be part of the curriculum.
- Design can complement the curriculum in form of a project or external offer like a workshop or summer school.

- Design as a thinking model can be used as an overall framework/method in all subjects.

These three possibilities have been elaborated, explored and put into practice by various international researchers and professionals. Within the framework of our research though, design as a subject is of minor interest and we will concentrate on the second and third identified way to embed design in education, as these regard design as an approach.

Three cases have been selected and are presented in this paper in order to clarify the ways to apply design in education.

The Sorrell Foundation Young Design Programme

The program offers specific design projects run in parallel to the schools curricula activities in cooperation with design students and professionals.

The Sorrell Foundation Young Design Programme brings design into schools by running a professional design project with pupils as clients commissioning a project contributing their school. The program started in England in 2005 as a collaborative project with students working in the public sector. Each project is running over 3-6 month with a team of children, art students and professional designers and architects working together. It aims to build up children's life skills by learning about and through the creative process.

Throughout the whole project all participants strengthen their competencies and develop transferable skills such as team working and communication, that the children can not only use for future school problems but for their everyday life. A great challenge is the identification and definition of the project itself which reflects the designers ability to identify and also redefine problems. The project, by being located in the children's school context, shows them the impact their action can have.

Studio H

This project teaches design and design thinking in a community context, away from the school environment, assisted by professionals.

Studio H was founded in 2009 by two creatives working together at Project H Design, Emily Pilloton a product designer and Matthew Miller an architect. It offers a one-year design curriculum to Junior-year students of the Bertie County school district in North Carolina (USA). The two designers themselves plus a range of experts and professionals work together with the students on projects for the community benefit. Every project reacts on the students environment and demands them to think about their community, critically reflect on it and respond to the local needs. This active problem solving provides them with techniques to deal with wicked problems and complex structures and encourages them to be active citizens.

The model is based on the principles of design as a (wicked-) problem solving competence, as being human centered and critical. All this is embedded in a holistic learning context, with a complex, not defined problem; a changing community and an interdisciplinary team. The project connects the students as well as the communities "Alltagskultur" in this context and creates a meaningful learning process, by converging subjects from the students daily life and using them as objects of discussion.

Education by design

The concept of implementing design thinking as a framework to elementary education is also being researched by Fontoura (2002). The project called Educação através do Design - EdaDe (Education by Design) has been developed as a research project in Brazil and creates a theoretical framework and accomplishment based on contextual experiments. It is now being applied through small projects by master students and researchers of the Postgraduate program in Design at Universidade Federal do Paraná.

The EdaDe is based on the constructivism theories that the children is responsible for building up its own knowledge. Through design activities that are

part of the curriculum, the children develop ways of learning the content (science, maths, geography and so) by applying on the design of products (tangible or intangibles) and following a project framework.

Based on his research Fontoura (2002) gives answers on the question of why it is possible to educate children by design: He highlights aspects related to a higher interest (by enjoying the projects); development of craft and social skills (by dealing with different material, process and teamwork); stimulation to curiosity and multidisciplinary approach (by dealing with unknown subjects that ask for knowledge from different areas) and self-awareness and conciseness (by reflecting about the new product and its impact in the society/ environment).

All three above presented approaches to embed design in public education have advantages as well as limitations regarding efficiency and applicability. It is important to remember that those experiences have been applied in a specific context and culture. Its diffusion and implementation in other realities would demand strong adjustments in order to be culturally adopted.

DISCUSSION

There seems to be no question about the fact, that the fast changes in society, technology etc that happen on global scale need reflection inside education. But although new guidelines has been released to react on these shifts, German elementary education puts the academic qualification of the children - the preparation for their future academic career - first. This is also the main criteria for the selection of pupils in elementary education before being placed in one of the secondary school types. Only second is the preparation for life through the development of social and cognitive competencies. This paper defends that the problems connected to those competencies are not tame problems but wicked problems. Children need to be educated to deal with those, which demands a new approach at schools.

HYPOTHESES 1: DESIGN IS “ALLTAGSKULTUR”

Design thinking appears as one of the possible answers to educate pupils not only to solve tame problems but also to develop strategies for wicked problems. Its educational value lies in the development of cognitive skills and abilities in real world problem solving (Fox 1981; Cross). Within a particular problem and its context a combination of implicit and explicit design knowledge can be applied. Especially the above presented case of Studio H is a great example of how design can be implemented into school education to create an extra value for the pupils as well as for the community they live and work within. Its success proves this hypothesis right.

All the world is designed by humans. Design forms, structures, simplifies all instances of human life. (SCHWERMER, 2007). Making this reality part of the curriculum can raise the interest and enthusiasm for school projects and bridge the gap between the formal school environment and students life. Design in this case can be the tool to merge education with reality and childrens interests and needs.

HYPOTHESES 2: DESIGN IS INTERDISCIPLINARY

Education by design happens transcend subject areas and boundaries. In schools, it can be applied as a framework to teach various subjects in one project. This way, the complexity of problems, information and networks, can be simulated. Moreover the design approach promotes teamwork in order to better understand problems and to create better solutions. Transferred to their lives, children can use these skills to better understand social and economic contexts.

HYPOTHESES 3: DESIGN IS SOLUTION-ORIENTED

Design acts future-oriented in project practice and the conception of new things. This solution-oriented thinking includes a change away from linear structured tasks to the possible of trial and failure. This promotes thought and personal growth of the children and demands a combination of creative and critical thinking.

DESIGN KNOWLEDGE IN THE CURRICULUM

The teaching of a way of thinking can be partly regarded as tacit knowledge, explained by Polanyi (1966) as knowledge we are not able to explain or even aware of, but that we can apply on various contexts, partly as explicit knowledge. Referring to a model of three levels of how strategic knowledge in design can be exercised that Cross (2006) developed, the contextualization of these two types of knowledge would be the highest level to aim for.

In 2008 when the German Ministry of School and Education modified the curricula for German elementary education, they gave more room to the development of thinking models and problem solving strategies. In practice school teachers try to educate their pupils as competent, critical citizens being able to tackle future challenges but struggle with time and school regulations. But still, German elementary education is undergoing some positive transformation. And this phase of rethinking and restructuring of school education opened the way for new teaching methods and presented a move away from linear instruction. It even created the opportunity to implement design thinking and its qualities and characteristics as described above in schools. This is why the overall aim for the future must be, to not only implement design to the elementary education, but the whole system should be changed to provide a new thinking adjusted to today's and future needs and requirements.

OUTLOOK

This paper does represent the state of the art of our research and a common ground of design, design thinking and education theories relevant for both our research topics. It does serve as an insight into the problematic without claiming to be holistic. To stress our point we followed one route, but being aware that contrary theories exist. As one example the theory of design as a third area in education (besides the sciences and humanities) might be quoted. It has enthusiastic advocates, f.e. Bruce Archer and Nigel Cross, but is on the contrary heavily discussed by other theorists from design, social studies and sciences. Evaluating these opposing theories will be one major part of our future research.

We are aware that the solution suggested in this paper is not systematic and can't be applied as a new state education policy but instead it has to be adopted and adapted for each school individually. Moreover, integrating design in the school is a time consuming strategy once you can't repeat classes and the content and strategy has to change due to different contexts. It would need more teachers to prepare and guide classes and a great amount of trust into the kids as there is never a predefined aim or solution to reach. The work on self defined aims asks for a great amount of self reflection of the kids and an attentive attendance of the teacher.

In our ongoing master studies, we will use the knowledge base, laid out in this paper, to identify and discuss models for design education and education through design.

The more applied theories on German elementary education will be carried on in Jeannette Webers study on "A culture of learning in urban context" and will be situated in troubled urban neighbourhoods in Germany. Research will be conducted in elementary schools and extended to non-formal learning environments. The next step of this project will be the implementation of a design project in an elementary school based on the findings presented in this paper. Based on the new findings some thoughts of this paper might have to be reconsidered.

Aim of both research-projects is, despite the theoretical evaluation, the development of a practical approach for the future of learning through, with or about design.

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